

Indo-Usa: Natural Partners- Quadrilateral Dialogue

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Abstract: Defence has emerged as a major pillar of our relationship. America has designated India as a “Major Defence partner” in that it promised to facilitate defence trade and technology-sharing with India to a level at par with that of the United States’ closest allies and partners. The wide-reaching changes in the world order coupled with geo-political shifts in the world with diffusion of the US dominance, rise of China and its intimidating stance in the Indo-Pacific region and beyond has prompted the United States to seek India on its side. The present study has been carried out to study the different aspects of Quadrilateral partnership between India and USA. For this purpose the researcher has used both primary and secondary data. a self structured questionnaire has been applied for data collection from a sample of 150 people identified by random sampling method. For secondary sources the researcher has followed different types of books journals and internet sources. Simple percentage system has been used for data analysis and graphical presentation has also been used for data analysis.

Keywords: Defence, Technology, Partnership, Indo-Pacific Region, India, United States.

Introduction:

U.S.-India ties are a “natural partnership of shared endeavors” India’s Prime Minister Atal Behari Vajpayee said in his speech to the U.S Congress in year 2000.¹ Same sentiments were expressed by President Obama in his address to the Indian parliament during his visit of India in 2015 “India and the US could have a defining partnership, “The world will be better if we stand together. I believe America can be India's best partner”.² On this, PM Modi in his address to the US congress in 2016 said that, “India and the U.S. have overcome the hesitations of history” and called for the “stronger economic and defense ties between the two countries.

The "updated Quad" is a new attempt to promote a "rules-based order in the Indo-Pacific" and is the 2017 update to the informal quadrilateral security conversation that was initially created by the US, Japan, India, and Australia in 2007. ¹ The Quad's resuscitation, however, creates more gaps than it does openings. These don't only focus on the goals and aspirations of its members. They also talk about what the term "Indo-Pacific" means as a region, why it requires more institutional backing, and if the Quad 2.0 is the right organisation. This article begins with outlining the Quad before moving on to talk about the partners' unique interests. The main potential areas for cooperation and potential obstacles are then outlined. It concludes by assessing the Quad's chances. Although there is the possibility for future low-key cooperation, the policy brief argues that there is a significant

risk that increased geopolitical competition would waste these opportunities. The vagueness of the phrase "Indo-Pacific" and the absence of Indonesia ultimately restrict the Quad's ability to support an Indo-Pacific order.

The quadrilateral security dialogue, or "Quad," was resurrected in 2017 to create a "rules-based order in the Indo-Pacific." The US, Japan, India, and Australia are all members of the Quad, which was first created as a way to respond to the 2004 tsunami that struck the Indian Ocean. However, it quickly fell apart in 2008 as a consequence of escalating strategic competition across Asia. Despite the four countries' sometimes divergent views on the regional strategic developments, the Quad's revival suggests a better convergence of interests this time. The Quad, however, still has serious viability problems. First of all, it's doubtful that the four main nations will be able to utilise opportunities for cooperation without allowing the alliance to be once again swamped by greater geopolitical competition. Second, given that Indonesia has been revived to support this "Indo-Pacific" order, the Quad is constrained by the vagueness of the Indo-Pacific concept and its absence.

Background of the Study: The tsunami that hit the Indian Ocean in December 2004 led to the formation of the first quadrilateral collaboration. In order to help in the coordination of relief efforts, the US, Japan, Australia, and India formed the "Tsunami Core Group" as one of its responses. This organisation was never designed to continue

since its main purpose was to deal with the immediate problems caused by the tsunami and its aftermath. 2 But the quadrilateral concept quickly changed into something else. 3 Japan was eager to form partnerships based on shared principles in order to construct a "arc of freedom and prosperity" around the area. 4 In order to consider additional possibilities for future participation, the four countries met at the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) Regional Forum conference in the Philippines in August 2007. Later that year, they took part in significant naval drills with Singapore, which drew condemnation from China. These early attempts at collaboration, meanwhile, merely widened the gaps on the Quad's main goal. By 2008, Australia withdrew from talks "of that sort" after raising objections to the Quad and its potential effects on Sino-Australian ties. India was concerned about how the Quad may affect its own foreign policy. 7 Later, the Quad lacked some of its lustre and was mostly abandoned by national diplomacy. But the Quad was still there; it was just taking a vacation. 2017 saw a rise in interest in the subject. 8 As a result, the four nations picked up their conversation again and convened in the Philippines once again, this

time in connection with the East Asia Summit. Later, they made a commitment to strive toward "deepening relationship based in shared values and principles and continuous discussions."

Research Question: The researcher has formulated the following research question for the study-

1. Will the Quad contribute to the Indo-Pacific region's stability and peace?
2. How crucial is the Quad for the Indo-Pacific region's security and prosperity?
3. How do you believe the Quad would change the security landscape in your nation?
4. What are the Quad's prospects?

Methodology: Considering the research questions the researcher has followed the survey type research. For the current study a self structured questionnaire has been applied for data collection from a sample of 150 people identified by random sampling method. Simple percentage system has been used for data analysis and graphical presentation has also been used for the current study. It also uses the secondary sources of information. For secondary sources the researcher has followed different types of books journals and internet sources.

Data Analysis

The Quad will contribute to stability and peace of the Indo-Pacific region

Item	Options	Response(%)
The Indo-Pacific area will become more stable and peaceful thanks to the Quad.	Strongly agree	18%
	Agree	38%
	Neither agree nor disagree	29%
	Disagree	11%
	Strongly disagree	4%

It is evident from the above table and figure that 18% people respond strongly agree to the view The Indo-Pacific area will benefit

from the Quad's stability and peace, according to 29% of respondents. 4% strongly disagree, leaving 11% in disagreement.

How important is the Quad for security and prosperity of the Indo-Pacific region?

Item	Opinions	Response
How crucial is the Quad for the Indo-Pacific region's security and prosperity?		
	It is necessary for sustaining the regional power balance	33%
	It has diplomatic and symbolic value	39%
	It will become the critical initiative to ensure a free and open Indo pacific	18%
	Other	10%

The above table shows that in response to the question “How important is the Quad for security and prosperity of the Indo-Pacific region?” 33% responds that ‘It will become the crucial effort to secure a free and open

Indo-Pacific, say 18% of respondents, while 39% say it has diplomatic and symbolic importance. It is vital for maintaining the regional power balance.

How do you think the Quad could affect your country’s security environment?

Item	Options	Response
How do you think the Quad could affect your country’s security environment	It is too debatable and may contribute to a regional arms race.	15%
	Although it may increase regional tension, it won't significantly improve my country's security condition.	30%
	It is a positive move, and it will make our nation safer.	32%
	It won't even make a difference.	14%
	Other	9%

It is evident from the above table that regarding the question “How do you think the Quad could affect your country’s security environment?” 15% people respond that It is too contentious and might contribute to a regional arms race, according to 30% of

respondents, who also claim that it won't improve my country's security condition; Our nation will be safer, according to 32% of respondents, while 9% of individuals express alternative opinions.

What are the Quad’s prospects?

Item	Options	Response
What are the chances for the Quad?	The Quad will become more and more important.	15%
	Depending on how active or pushy China	23%
	will be in the maritime sphere Depending on how aggressive/assertive	31%
	China will generally be The Quad is a scam that will vanish (again)	19%
	Other	12%

The above table clearly depicts that in response to the question “What are the Quad’s prospects?” 15 % respond is “The Quad will grow increasingly more significant’. Whereas 31% are of the opinion that ‘It depends how assertive/aggressive China will be in general’. 19% people agree that the Quad will disappear again and 12% people are of another opinion.

Findings: The present study has found out the following-

The Quad for security and prosperity of the Indo-Pacific region has diplomatic and symbolic value.

The Quad has multi dimensional prospects

The Quad will become more and more important.

It will increase regional tension but won't significantly improve my country's security condition.

It is a positive move, and it will make our nation safer.

Conclusion: The categorization of the Quad as antagonistic against China may be accepted by the region, or at least understood. A lot of individuals think that the Quad or some similar arrangement is necessary because of China's perceived assertiveness. However, those who are uneasy and worried about the potential

worsening of hostility are adamant that it won't immediately harm their country. Consequently, the criticism of the Quad cannot serve as the basis for the argument against it. The real question is whether the Quad members' inaction and lack of leadership will cause it to "slip" once more. The main issue is a lack of understanding. Respondents cited the Quad's lack of clarity as its primary problem, not just as an explanation for their mixed feelings toward it. If the Quad actors (both members and supporters) fail to adequately address these concerns, they run the risk of leaving a void that might be filled with widely disseminated misconceptions.

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